

CRYSTALLISATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF NOVEL SEMI ORGANIC NON-LINEAR OPTICAL CRYSTAL: GLYCINIUM OXALATE

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Abstract:

Nonlinear optical amino acid single crystals of pure glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals were successfully grown by slow evaporation solution growth method. The grown crystals were subjected to different characterization studies in order to test its suitability for device fabrication. X-ray diffraction studies were carried out to examine the lattice parameters and crystallinity nature. The presence of various functional groups and their modes of vibration were identified using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectral analysis. Optical spectral studies have been carried out to find the band gap and optical constants of the material. The lower cut off wavelength and the transparency region has been analysed using UV-Vis spectral studies. CHNS studies were used to analyse the elemental compositions of the grown crystals. Mechanical strength of the grown samples were tested by Vickers micro hardness and various parameters like work hardening coefficient, elastic stiffness constant and minimum level of indentation load has been calculated. The method adopted for crystal growth and the results obtained through various characterizations are analysed and interpreted in detail.

Key Words: Crystal Growth, Non-Linear Optics, Microhardness & Second Harmonic Generation

1. Introduction:

Nonlinear optical (NLO) materials have been playing a vital role in industrial applications. These materials show a significant impact on laser technology, optical communications and optical data storage etc. Crystals of amino acid complexes with the simple inorganic salts exhibit interesting physical properties from the application point of view. Hence in the recent years much of the work has been aimed at synthesizing semi-organic NLO crystals in particular glycine complexes, with better chemical stability, SHG efficiency, laser damage threshold, thermal and mechanical properties [1].

Glycine (NH₂CH₂COOH amino acetic acid) is the simplest amino acid, which is hydrophilic polar in nature. It is the only protein-forming amino acid without a center of chirality. Glycine helps to trigger the release of oxygen to the energy requiring cell-making process. It is necessary for the manufacture of hormones in the human biological system that builds a strong immune system [2]. Glycine exhibits polymorphism. It grows in many forms; such as the stable α form and γ - form and the unstable form. The crystal of α - form is metastable in aqueous solution and it transforms into γ -form spontaneously. While glycine can exist as a neutral molecule in the gas phase, it exists as zwitterions in solution and in the solid.

Glycine oxalate, another nonlinear optical crystal, in the family of glycine derivative [3]. The single crystal analysis was performed and they have reported that the glycine molecule exists in the cationic form with a positively charged amino group and an uncharged carboxylic acid group, while the oxalic acid molecule exists in a mono-ionized state in the crystals. The hydrogen bonds that stabilize the molecules are interconnected between the amino and carboxyl groups of adjacent molecules, in a head to tail arrangement. In each layer, the unlike molecules are connected through O-H-O hydrogen bond between the carboxyl group of the amino acid and the carboxylate group of the semi-oxalate ion and their symmetry equivalents. The double layers are held together by possible C-H-O and Vander Waals interactions.

2. Importance of the Work:

The perspective of understanding a system where the hydrogen bonding plays a fundamental role has stimulated this interest. Excellent optical quality, high thermal stability, high laser damage threshold makes glycine oxalate crystals, a strong candidate for NLO applications. Glycine oxalate crystals usually display large nonlinear optical (NLO) response and are potential candidates for applications in the emerging areas of photonics [4]. They also play vital role in second-harmonic generation (SHG), frequency mixing, electro-optic modulation, optical parametric oscillation, optical image processing, colour displays, underwater communications and medical diagnostics etc.

3. Experimental:

A glass beaker has been taken and cleaned with acetone and rinsed with double distilled water thoroughly in order to remove the organic and inorganic moistures present. Glycine and oxalic acid salts were weighed in 1:1 ratio and taken separately. The compositions were dissolved in 25ml of distilled water and stirred

well using a temperature controlled magnetic stirrer to yield a homogeneous mixture of solution. After 4 hours of continuous stirring the solution is removed and filtered using good quality filter paper to remove suspended impurities and then allowed to crystallize under slow evaporation. The solution should be kept undisturbed in room temperature for the growth of bulk single crystals. The glycini-um oxalate crystals were grown and harvested in a period of 3 to 4 weeks successfully.

The same procedure has been followed to synthesize pure glycine crystals. Fully grown crystals were harvested in a period of 2 to 3 weeks. The images of as grown glycine and glycini-um oxalate crystals are shown in Fig 3.1 and Fig 3.2 respectively.

Figure 3.1: As grown crystals of pure glycine

Figure 3.2: As grown crystals of glycini-um oxalate

4. Results and Discussion:

Structural Studies:

4.1 Powder X- Ray Diffraction Analysis: Powder X-ray Diffraction (XRD) is one of the primary techniques used by mineralogists and solid-state chemists to examine the Physico-chemical make-up of unknown materials [5]. Finely crushed powder of pure glycine and glycini-um oxalate crystal was subjected to powder X-ray diffraction analysis employing a SIEFERT 3003 TT diffractometer with a characteristic $\text{CuK}\alpha$ (1.540589 Å) radiation for structural analysis. The sample scanned in the 2θ values from 10° to 70° . Fig 4.1 shows the Powder XRD spectrum of both the grown crystals. The characteristic peak has appeared at 29.31° (2θ) for glycine and at around 29.61° for glycini-um oxalate crystals. Compared with the standard JCPDS values the glycine crystallizes in the hexagonal crystal system whereas glycini-um oxalate crystallizes in monoclinic system and the space group is found to be as P21/c.

Figure 4.1: Powder x-ray spectrum of glycine and glycini-um oxalate crystals

The sharp peaks in Fig 4.1 indicate the crystallinity of the grown crystals. The observed prominent peaks are (0 3 1), (1 3 0) and (0 2 1). The above mentioned changes are due to the presence of the additive

oxalic acid into the lattice of glycine crystal. The observed results are in good agreement with the reported values.

4.1.1 Calculation of d-Spacing: The value of d (the interplanar spacing between the atoms) is calculated using [6]

Bragg's Law:

$$2d\sin\theta = n\lambda \quad (4.1)$$

$$d = \frac{\lambda}{2\sin\theta} \quad (4.2)$$

Equation 4.2 gives the d-spacing and the calculated values for pure glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals are tabulated in table 4.1 and table 4.2 respectively

Table 4.1: Observed and calculated d-spacing values of pure glycine

2 Theta	Theta	d observed	d calculated	Strain = (dob-dcal)/dcal
14.828	7.41	5.9694	5.9742	-0.0008
20.249	10.12	4.3820	4.3850	-0.00068
24.006	12.003	3.7039	3.7061	-0.00059
28.577	14.28	3.1211	3.1250	-0.00125
29.313	14.65	3.0444	3.0480	-0.00118
29.904	14.95	2.9855	2.9871	-0.00054

Table 4.2: Observed and calculated d-spacing values of glycinium oxalate

2 Theta	Theta	d observed	d calculated	Strain = $\frac{dob-dcal}{dcal}$
9.06	4.53	9.7450	9.7601	-0.00155
17.83	8.91	4.9704	4.9710	-0.00012
18.42	9.21	4.8115	4.8165	-0.00104
22.06	11.03	4.0251	4.0293	-0.00104
24.25	12.12	3.6673	3.6675	-0.00055
28.57	14.28	3.1210	3.1210	0
29.62	14.81	3.0132	3.0134	-0.00066
31.98	15.99	2.7963	2.7967	-0.00014
33.39	16.69	2.6806	2.6810	-0.00015
35.30	17.65	2.5404	2.5408	-0.00016
37.61	18.80	2.3895	2.3920	-0.00105

From both the tables it's clear that the calculated values are similar to the observed d-spacing values and the strain calculated is very less.

Vibrational Studies:

4.2 FTIR Spectral Analysis: Functional groups present in the sample have been analysed using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrum. The FTIR spectra of the grown crystals were recorded using KBr pellet technique in the region 4000 cm⁻¹ to 400 cm⁻¹ using JASCO FT-IR 460 Plus spectrometer. Vibrational analysis of glycinium oxalate crystals is performed based on the vibrations of glycinium ion consisting of amino, methylene, carboxylic acid groups and oxalate ion. The FTIR absorption spectrum of glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals are shown in Fig. 4.2 & Fig. 4.3 respectively.

Figure 4.2: FTIR spectrum of pure glycine crystal

Figure 4.3: FTIR spectrum of glycinium oxalate crystal

The spectrum reveals the characteristic vibrations of the zwitter ionic group, -NH₃⁺ and the carboxylate ions. The primary NH₃⁺ group has N-H stretching frequencies coinciding with the saturated C-H absorption frequencies [7]. Hence the vibrations of the saturated C-H absorption to be observed around 3000 cm⁻¹ are masked by the vibrations of the -NH₃⁺ ion and cause a broadened band in this range. This broadening is further widened due to the presence of N-H-O hydrogen bonding. The NH₂⁺ group present in the free acid is converted into the -NH₃⁺ ion during the formation of the salt.

Figure 4.3 shows a strong band at 1820 – 1660 cm⁻¹. This band usually is the most intense absorption band in a spectrum. It has medium width and this shows carbonyl C=O bend. Since O-H is also present. It has a broad absorption near 3300 – 2500 cm⁻¹. This actually will overlap the C-H stretch.

The symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of COO⁻ are positioned at 1614 cm⁻¹ and 1412 cm⁻¹ respectively in glycine crystals which is shown in Fig 4.2 (a). For saturated amines, it is established that the asymmetric NH₂ stretching will give rise to a band between 3380 and 3350 cm, while the symmetric stretching will appear between 3310 and 3280 cm [8]. Band found in 1743 cm⁻¹ denotes C=O stretching and this is due to the presence of oxalic acid in glycine. Observed bands and nature of the peak are assigned on the basis of characteristic vibrations and are shown in Table 4.3 for both the grown crystals

Table 4.3: FT-IR spectral assignments of glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals

Wave Number (cm ⁻¹)				Tentative Assignment
Glycine	Nature	Glycinium oxalate	Nature	
504	s	580	w	COO wagging mode/ CH ₂ out of plane bend
893	M	860	s	C-C stretching mode
908	w	900	m	NH ₃ rocking/CH ₂ rocking in
1032	m	1037	w	CH ₂ rocking out vibration
1111	m	1117	w	NH ₃ rocking
		1253	m	NH ₂ rocking
1332	s	1326	w	CH ₂ Wagging vibration
1412	w	1423	m	COO ⁻ symmetric stretching
1442	m	1433	w	CH ₂ bending deformation
1514	w	1594	w	NH ₃ ⁺ asymmetric stretching
		1743	m	C=O stretching
2619	w	2682	w	NH ₂ asymmetric stretching
3009	w	3000	w	CH ₂ asymmetric stretching
3169	m	3151	w	NH ₂ asymmetric stretching
3422	w	3411	m	NH ₃ asymmetric stretching

Optical Studies:

4.3 UV- Visible Spectral Analysis: The UV-Vis spectrum plays a vital role in identifying the potential of aNLO material because a given NLO material can be of utility only if it has a wide transparency window without any absorption at the fundamental and second harmonic wavelengths [9]. The optical studies were

performed for the grown crystal and the spectrum was recorded in the spectral region of 200 - 1100 nm using VARIAN CARY 5E spectrometer. The grown crystals of pure glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals were cut and polished to thickness of about 2 mm was subjected to absorption and transmission measurements.

4.3.1 Optical Transmission Analysis: The transmission spectrum plays a vital role in identifying the potential of a NLO material because a given NLO material can be of utility only if it has a wide transparency window without any absorption at the fundamental and second harmonic wavelengths [10]. Spectra for both the samples were plotted in the wavelength range 200-1100nm and are shown in Fig 4.4 (a) and Fig 4.5 (b) respectively.

Figure 4.4: (a) UV-Visible transmission spectrum of pure glycine

Figure 4.4: (b) UV-Visible transmission spectrum of glycinium oxalate

Both the crystals are found to be transparent in the entire visible region between 400 and 800 nm, which is sufficient for SHG laser radiation of 1064 nm for frequency doubling process. The cut-off wavelength of the glycine is observed at 200 nm, and the crystals show good transmittance of 100% in the range of 230–1100 nm. There is no appreciable absorption of light in the entire visible range as in the case of all amino acids [11]. Fig 4.4 (b) shows that for glycinium oxalate crystals transmittance starts increasing only after 230 nm that is from 200nm- 230nm there was no transmission and it also shows 97% of transmittance in the range 260-1100 and it is clear from Fig 4.4 (a) and Fig 4.4(b) that glycinium oxalate crystals have less transparency when compared to pure glycine crystals and this change is due to the presence of oxalic acid. The addition of oxalic acid gradually decreases the transparency of the crystals. Overall both the crystals show no absorption in the entire visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum. This shows the absence of any overtones and absorbance due to electronic transitions. It is also an important requirement for NLO materials having nonlinear optical applications [12]. Favourable transmittance of the crystal in the entire visible region suggests its suitability for second harmonic generation.

4.3.2 Optical Absorption Analysis: The absorbance spectrum plays a vital role in identifying the cut off wavelength of the particular crystal.

Figure 4.5: (a) UV-Visible absorbance spectrum of Glycine

Figure 4.5: (b) UV-Visible absorbance spectrum of Glycinium oxalate

The lower cut off wavelength for the grown pure glycine crystal was observed to be around 230 nm and is shown in Fig 4.5 (a) and the lower cut off wavelength of glycinium oxalate crystal is around 245 nm which is shown in Fig 4.5 (b) the shift in the cut off wavelength clearly shows the influence of oxalic acid in the pure glycine crystals. In both the crystals absorbance is found to be in the ultra-violet region and they lack absorbance in the rest of the region so there would be no visible sign of any light being absorbed. Thus both the grown crystals are found to be colourless.

4.3.3 Band Gap Determination Using Tauc's Plot: The dependence of optical absorption coefficient on photon energy helps to study the band structure and type of transition of electrons. The optical absorption coefficient (α) as calculated from transmittance using the following relation [13]

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{d} \ln(1/T) \quad (4.3)$$

Where T is the transmittance and d is the thickness of the crystal. The crystal under study had an absorption coefficient (α) obeying the following relation for high photon energies ($h\nu$):

$$\alpha = \frac{A(h\nu - E_g)}{h\nu} \quad (4.4)$$

Where E_g is the optical band gap of the crystal and A is a constant. A plot of variation of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ for both glycine and glycinium oxalate is shown in Fig 4.6 (a) and Fig 4.6 (b).

Figure 4.6: (a) Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ for the glycine crystal

Figure 4.6: (b) Plot of $(ah\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ for the glycinium oxalate crystal

E_g was evaluated using the extrapolation of the linear part. Using the Tauc plot in, the energy gap (E_g) of glycine was calculated to be 6eV and the large band gap clearly indicates the wide transparency of the crystal [14]. This high band gap value indicated that the grown crystal possessed dielectric behaviour to induce polarization when powerful radiation was incident on the material. The band gap of glycinium oxalate is found as 5.5 eV from Fig 4.6 (b) and this shows that the band gap has been reduced when compared to the pure glycine crystals. Therefore, gradual addition of oxalic acid in glycine crystals will increase the electrical conductivity of the crystal.

Elemental Studies:

4.4 CHNS Analysis: Qualitative and quantitative information forms the base of all material characterization. The CHNS analyser is specifically designed to determine carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur in organic materials. The chemical composition of the grown glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals determined by Carbon, Hydrogen, and Nitrogen (CHN) analysis using Thermo Finnegan Flash EA 1112 series is compared with the theoretical values in Table 4.3. From the results the molecular formula and molecular weight of glycine and glycinium oxalate is established as $C_2H_5NO_2$, 75.05 g/mole and $C_4H_7NO_6$, 164.48 g/mole respectively.

Table 4.4: CHN analysis data of pure Glycine and Glycinium oxalate single crystals

Element	Theoretical composition %		Measured composition %	
	Glycine	Glycinium oxalate	Glycine	Glycinium oxalate
Carbon	32.04	29.20	31.76	27.92
Hydrogen	6.72	4.28	7.02	4.60
Nitrogen	18.6	8.51	18.78	8.16

The experimental C, H and N percentages were compared with theoretical values and listed in Table 4.4 the experimental values are found to be close to the theoretical values which confirms the presence of the compound.

4.5 Mechanical Characterization: In order to understand the plasticity of the crystals, micro hardness tests were carried out on the grown crystals. The hardness of the crystals depends on type of chemical bonding, lattice energy, Debye temperature, heat of formation and interatomic spacing [15]. The good quality crystals are needed not only with good optical performance but with good mechanical behaviour. Hardness of the material is the resistance it offers to indentation by a much harder body.

4.5.1 Vicker's Micro Hardness Analysis: Micro hardness measurements were done for glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals using Leitz-Wetzlar hardness tester fitted with a Vickers diamond indenter at room temperature. When the mean diagonal of the indentation has been determined, the Vicker's hardness number can be calculated from the above formula.

$$H_V = 1.8544 P/d^2 \tag{4.5}$$

Where

H_V = Vickers hardness number

P = load in g

d = arithmetic mean of the two diagonals

Table 4.5: Micro hardness number of Glycine and Glycinium oxalate crystals

Load (g)	Micro hardness number H_V	
	Glycine	Glycinium oxalate
25	22.5	43.6
50	35.1	55.9
100	49.8	76.3

Graph is plotted between load and micro hardness number using the values given in Table 4.5

Figure 4.7: (a) Variation of micro hardness number vs load P of pure glycine

Fig 4.7 (b) Variation of micro hardness number vs load P of glycinium oxalate

A plot of micro hardness number versus load P for the grown glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals are shown in Fig 4.7(a) and Fig 4.7(b) respectively. From the graph it is found that for both the crystals as load increases hardness number also increases and this indicates that both the crystals exhibits Reverse Indentation Size Effect (RISE) but when compared to glycine the glycinium oxalate crystals have higher hardness value, since higher hardness value of a crystal indicates that greater stress is required to form dislocation thus confirming that greater crystalline perfection is found in glycinium oxalate rather than pure glycine.

Figure 4.8: (a) Variation of log d vs log P of glycine

Figure 4.8: (b) Variation of log d vs log P of glycinium oxalate

The plot of log P versus log d is a straight line and its slope gives work hardening index n, which is given in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Work hardening index n

Grown Crystal	Work hardening index n
Pure glycine	3.4
Glycinium oxalate	4.2

The work hardening index n of glycinium oxalate is found to be larger when compared to the pure glycine crystals. According to Onitsch [16], n should lie between 1 and 1.6 for harder materials and above 1.6 for softer materials. Since the work hardening index n of both the crystals are above 1.6 the grown crystals are found to be as softer materials. The elastic stiffness constant (C_{11}) were calculated for the grown crystals using Wooster's empirical relation as,

$$C_{11} = H_v^{7/4} \quad (4.6)$$

The yield strength of the material can be found using the formula

$$\sigma_v = H_v / 3 \quad (4.7)$$

The calculated values are given in Tables 4.7 and Table 4.8 for both grown glycine and glycinium oxalate crystals.

Table 4.7: Elastic stiffness constant and yield strength of pure glycine

Load P	Hv (N/mm ²)	$C_{11} \times 10^{14}$ Pa	σ_v (MPa)
25	22.5	2.3	7.5
50	35.1	5.0	11.7
100	49.8	9.3	16.6

Table 4.8: Elastic stiffness constant and yield strength of glycinium oxalate

Load P	Hv (N/mm ²)	$C_{11} \times 10^{14}$ Pa	σ_v (MPa)
25	43.6	7.3	14.5
50	55.9	11.4	18.6
100	76.3	19.6	25.4

Figure 4.9: (a) Load P vsdⁿ of Glycine

From table 4.7 and table 4.8 the stiffness constant C_{11} is found to be higher for glycinium oxalate crystals. The value of c_{11} gives the idea of toughness of bonding between neighbouring atom. Here, the higher value of c_{11} indicates that the binding forces between the ions are not quite strong and hence they could be used for most of the devices since Hardness is one of the important factor in selecting the processing (cutting, grinding, and polishing) steps of bulk in the fabrication of devices based on the crystals [17]. Glycine has got less stiffness value hence the binding forces are not much stronger as glycinium oxalate crystals. According to Meyer's relation

$$P = k_1 d^n \tag{4.8}$$

Where k_1 is the standard hardness value which can be obtained from the plot of P versus d^n and is shown in Fig 4.9 (a) and Fig 4.9 (b) for both the crystals.

Figure 4.9: (b) Load P vs d^n of Glycinium oxalate

The standard hardness value K_1 of glycine crystals are found to be as 8.443 from Figure 4.9 (a) and Figure 4.9 (b) gives the standard hardness value of glycinium oxalate crystals and the calculated value is 0.7787. These values are substituted in Hays and Kendall equation to calculate the minimum level of indentation load W . Hays and Kendall proposed a relationship to calculate W by the equation [18]

$$d_n = \frac{w}{k_1} + \left(\frac{k_2}{k_1}\right) d^2 \tag{4.9}$$

The plot between d_n and d^2 shown in Fig. 4.10 (a) and Fig 4.10 (b), gives a straight line having slope (k_2/k_1) .

Figure 4.10: (a) Plot between d^2 and d^n for glycine

Figure 4.10: (b) Plot between d^2 and d^n for glycinium oxalate

From the graphs shown in Fig 4.10 (a) and Fig 4.10 (b), the slope (k_2/k_1) is found to be as 521.2 and 9309 respectively for both the grown crystals. From these values, the minimum level of indentation load W was calculated to be 8.425 g for glycine whereas for glycinium oxalate the minimum level of indentation load W was found to be as 21.52 g. From this analysis, it is clear that in case of glycine the plastic deformation starts at a very early stage that is cracks start developing on the smooth surface of the glycine crystals beyond 8.425 g, thus the yield point is attained at a very early stage compared to glycinium oxalate whereas in glycinium oxalate the crystals deform elastically prior to the minimum level of indentation load 21.52g which is found to be much higher than the pure glycine crystals and beyond that the deformation becomes plastic and permanent thus cracks start developing on the surface of the crystals [19]. The micro-indentation test is a useful method for the study of the nature of plastic flow and its influence on the deformation of the material [20]. From the micro

hardness analysis of the both crystals it is found that glycini-um oxalate crystals are much harder and have got a good crystalline perfection and also the plastic deformation starts only after the minimum level of indentation load of 21.52g which makes the crystal more prominent in fabrication of devices.

Conclusion:

Single crystals of pure glycine and glycini-um oxalate crystals were successfully grown by slow evaporation solution grown technique. High resolution powder X-ray diffractometer study reveals the crystalline perfection of the crystal. The presence of different vibrational modes of the fundamental groups present in the compound has been confirmed using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopic studies. Optical transmission spectrum reveals that the pure glycine has 100% transmission whereas its lower in case of glycini-um oxalate where only 97% transmission is observed. Both the crystals are found to be transparent in the entire visible region. The lower cut off wavelength of glycine is found to be around 230 nm and for glycini-um oxalate it was found as 245 nm. Band gap E_g calculated from tauc plot showed that glycini-um oxalate has lower band gap compared to pure glycine crystals hence this fact reveals that addition of oxalic acid increases electrical conductivity of glycine crystals. From CHNS analysis it is clear that the theoretical composition of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen are found almost equal to the measured values and this also confirms the presence of above mentioned compounds in the grown crystals. Micro hardness analysis showed that the glycini-um oxalate have greater crystalline perfection than the pure glycine crystals. Calculated elastic stiffness constant and yield strength revealed that the binding forces between the ions are found to be stronger in glycini-um oxalate crystals rather than the pure glycine crystals. The minimum level of indentation load was found to be 8.42 g for glycine crystals whereas for glycini-um oxalate it was found to be as 21.52 g. comparatively glycini-um oxalate crystals are found to be much harder and have a good crystalline perfection which makes it suitable for fabrication of devices.

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